

Adsorption Studies from Current-time Curves

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The influence of surfactants on electrode reactions is explicable on the basis of the role of adsorption at the electrode surface¹. The effects of adsorption on the shapes of polarographic steps are studied conveniently by means of *c-t* curves of single polarised mercury drops. Lorenz², Mockel³, Muller⁴, Heyrovsky, Sorm and Forejt⁵ and Frumkin⁶ have given definite evidences for the formation of films of a surface-active material at the polarised mercury drop. The formation of adsorbed films is due to specific adsorption which is preceded by the transport of the adsorbable molecules to the interface. Thus, these are transferred from the solution layer to the adsorption layer which may be followed by processes viz. association, condensation or nucleation.

In the present short communication, kinetics of film formation have been studied in presence of surfactants triton X-100, Ascorbic acid and Eosin. Pb (II) 2 mM in 0.1 M KCl was used as the depolarizer. Lange's polarometer in conjunction with a Lange's Pen recorder and Multiflex galvanometer were used for the record of *c-t* curves. The capillary had the characteristics $m^{\frac{2}{3}} t^{\frac{1}{3}} = 1.90 \text{ mg.}^{\frac{2}{3}} \text{ sec.}^{-\frac{1}{3}}$ and all measurements were made at 25°.

FIG 1. *C-t* CURVES FOR Pb(II) IN PRESENCE OF VARYING CONC. OF TRITON X-100 AT -0.5 V.

a - $0.5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$,
 b - $2.5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$,
 c - $6.3 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$.

Fig. 1.

1. P. Zuman and I. M. Kolthoff, "Progress in Polarography", Interscience Pub. Inc. N.Y. Vol. I, p. 96, 1962.
2. W. Z. Lorenz, *Physik Chem.* (Frankfurt) 1958, **18**, 1.
3. W. Lorenz and F. Mockel, *Z. Electrochem.*, 1956, **60**, 507, 939.
4. W. Lorenz and W. Muller, *Z. Physik Chem.*, (Frankfurt) (New Folge), 1958, **18**, 141.
5. J. Heyrovsky, F. Sorm and J. Forejt; *Collection Czech Chem. Commun.*, 1947, **12**, 11.
6. A. N. Frumkin and V. I. Melik-Gaikazyan, *Doklady Akad. Nauk S.S.S.R.*, 1951, **77**, 1855.

The c-t curves of figure 1. may be explained qualitatively based on a diffusion controlled film formation process. At the very growth of a mercury drop, the surface-active material diffuses to the drop surface and adsorbs on it. In the early life of the drop, the surface-active material reaching the surface by diffusion is insufficient to retard the electrode process, but at the instant of maturation of the drop, sufficient SAS reaches the surface, bringing thereby a considerable deceleration of the electrode process and current is reduced to zero at the instant of complete coverage. In presence of higher concentration of SAS, lesser time is required for the coverage of the drop.

Koryta⁷ derived the kinetics of film formation on a mercury drop with the help of Ilkovic equation, taking diffusion as rate-controlling factor. During the growth of a drop, there is space on its surface for $0.85 m^{3/2} t^{3/2} \bar{l}_s$ moles of adsorbed substance (\bar{l}_s = maximum no. of moles adsorbed per cm^2),

A. C-t CURVES FOR Pb(II) IN ASCORBIC ACID.
(i) $5 \times 10^{-4}M$ (ii) $6 \times 10^{-4}M$ (iii) $8 \times 10^{-4}M$ (iv) $10^{-3}M$.

B. PLOT OF $1/C^2$ MOLE⁻² LITRE² VS. t SEC.
FOR ASCORBIC ACID

FIG. 2.

The no. of moles that have diffused to the surface by time t is

$$N_s = 0.732 \times 10^{-3} C_A D_A^{\frac{1}{2}} m^{\frac{3}{2}} \theta^{\frac{7}{2}}$$

$$\therefore \bar{S} = \frac{NS}{q} = 7.36 \times 10^{-4} C_A D_A^{\frac{1}{2}} \theta^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

$$\text{or } \theta = 1.82 \times 10^6 \frac{\bar{S}^2}{D_A C_A^2}$$

where \bar{S} = no. of moles per cm^2 mercury surface at surface saturation ; C_A = Bulk concentration of adsorbable substance in moles/litre ; D_A = Diffusion coefficient of SAS in $\text{cm}^2 \text{sec}^{-1}$.

The validity of above equation has been examined from the record of c - t curves by comparing θ , the time when the drop surface is just covered, with t° , the time when it reaches zero. t° is found by extrapolation to zero current, \bar{S} for ascorbic acid, eosin and triton X-100 are evaluated.

(a) *Ascorbic acid*

A plot of t° vs. $1/C^2$ (where C is the concentration of ascorbic acid) yields a straight line (Fig. 2) with the slope $4.57 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mole}^2 \text{ sec. litre}^{-2}$. If θ correspondse to t° , this slope should equal $1.82 \times 10^6 \frac{\bar{S}^2}{D_A}$. The number of moles per cm^2 , \bar{S} can be calculated according to

$$1.82 \times 10^6 \frac{\bar{S}^2}{D_A} = 4.57 \times 10^{-7}$$

D_A° for ascorbic acid in 0.1 N KCl = $10.25 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ sec}^{-1}$

$$\bar{S} = 1.603 \times 10^{-9} \text{ mole cm}^{-2}$$

(b) *Eosin*

Film formation for eosin molecules was shown by Wiesner⁹. For various concentrations of eosin, the wave height decreased on increasing its bulk concentration. From the record of c - t curves for various concentrations of eosin, t° were found. A straight line from the plot of $1/C^2$ vs. t° with a slope $3 \times 10^{-11} \text{ mole}^2 \text{ sec.}$ was obtained D_A° for eosin

$$= 6.7 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ sec}^{-1}$$

$$\bar{S} = 1.05 \times 10^{-11} \text{ mole/cm}^2$$

(c) *Triton X-100*

The diffusion coefficient D , of triton X-100 was found from the formula

$$D = \frac{3.32 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^2/\text{sec at } 25^\circ}{(V_m)^{\frac{1}{2}}}$$

where V_m = Apparent molal volume = $\frac{\text{Mol Wt.}}{\text{density}} = \frac{628}{0.888}$

8. J. Heyrovsky and J. Kuta, "Principles of Polarography", Academic Press, N.Y. 1966 p. 106.
9. K. Wiesener, *Collection Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1947, 12, 594.

The molecular weight and density were obtained from the Hand book of Surfactants by M/s Rohm Haas & Co.

$$D = 8.27 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2/\text{sec.}$$

A straight line from the plot of $1/C_A^2$ vs. t° yielded a slope of $4.8 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mole}^2 \text{ sec.}$

$$[\bar{S}] = 1.48 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mole/cm}^2 \text{ for triton X-100 is obtained.}$$

Thus, the distortions in polarographic steps, drawn out waves for the depolarizer (deceleration of electron transfer) are explicable from the record of c-t curves and assumption of adsorbed films on the drop surface.

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